

ON THE FROBENIUS PROBLEM FOR GEOMETRIC SEQUENCES

Amitabha Tripathi

Department of Mathematics, Indian Institute of Technology, Hauz Khas, New Delhi – 110016, India
 atripath@maths.iitd.ac.in

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Abstract

Let a, b, k be positive integers, with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$, and let \mathcal{A} denote the geometric sequence $a^k, a^{k-1}b, \dots, ab^{k-1}, b^k$. Let $\Gamma(\mathcal{A})$ denote the set of integers that are expressible as a linear combination of elements of \mathcal{A} with non-negative integer coefficients. We determine $g(\mathcal{A})$ and $n(\mathcal{A})$ which denote the *largest* (respectively, the *number* of) positive integer(s) not in $\Gamma(\mathcal{A})$. We also determine the set $\mathcal{S}^*(\mathcal{A})$ of positive integers not in $\Gamma(\mathcal{A})$ which satisfy $n + \Gamma^*(\mathcal{A}) \subset \Gamma^*(\mathcal{A})$, where $\Gamma^*(\mathcal{A}) = \Gamma(\mathcal{A}) \setminus \{0\}$.

1. Introduction

For a sequence of relatively prime positive integers $A = a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k$, let $\Gamma(A)$ denote the set of all integers of the form $\sum_{i=1}^k a_i x_i$ where each $x_i \geq 0$. It is well known and not difficult to show that $\Gamma^c(A) := \mathbb{N} \setminus \Gamma(A)$ is a *finite* set. The *Coin Exchange Problem* of Frobenius is to determine the *largest* integer in $\Gamma^c(A)$. This is denoted by $g(A)$, and called the Frobenius number of A . The Frobenius number is known in the case $k = 2$ to be $g(a_1, a_2) = a_1 a_2 - a_1 - a_2$, but is generally otherwise unsolved except in some special cases. A related problem is the determination of the number of integers in $\Gamma^c(A)$, which is denoted by $n(A)$ and known in the case $k = 2$ to be given by $n(a_1, a_2) = (a_1 - 1)(a_2 - 1)/2$. More complete information on the Frobenius problem may be found in [3].

Ong and Ponomarenko recently determined the Frobenius number for geometric sequences in [2]. If we denote the geometric sequence $a^k, a^{k-1}b, \dots, ab^{k-1}, b^k$ by $\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)$, and the corresponding Frobenius number by $G_k = g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$, Ong & Ponomarenko proved their claim by showing that the sequence $\{G_k\}_{k \geq 1}$ satisfies a certain first order recurrence, and then using induction. The main purpose of this note is to show that both the Frobenius number $g(A)$ and $n(A)$ follow in the case of geometric sequences from an old reduction formula due to Johnson [1] and Rödseth [4]. We further determine the set \mathcal{S}^* , introduced in [5], in the case of geometric sequences. This gives another proof of the result for the Frobenius number since $g(A)$ is the largest integer in $\mathcal{S}^*(A)$.

2. Main Results

Throughout this section, for positive integers a, b, k with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$, we denote by $\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)$ the geometric sequence $a^k, a^{k-1}b, \dots, ab^{k-1}, b^k$. We derive the values of both $g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) := G_k$ and $n(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) := N_k$ by two methods. We first use a well-known reduction formula to derive recurrence relations for the two sequences $\{G_k\}_{k \geq 1}$ and $\{N_k\}_{k \geq 1}$, and then use telescoping sums to solve each recurrence. The second method to derive $g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$ consists in showing that $\mathcal{S}^*(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$ has exactly one element, which must then be $g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$. Our second proof of the result for $n(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$ is indirect; we show that $2n(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) - 1 = g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$. We first recall the reduction formula that is central to our first derivation.

Lemma 1. ([1, 4]) *Let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k be positive integers. If $\gcd(a_2, \dots, a_k) = d$ and $a_j = da'_j$ for each $j > 1$, then*

- (a) $g(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) = dg(a_1, a'_2, \dots, a'_k) + a_1(d - 1)$;
- (b) $n(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) = dn(a_1, a'_2, \dots, a'_k) + \frac{1}{2}(a_1 - 1)(d - 1)$.

Theorem 1. *Let a, b, k be positive integers, with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$. Let $\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)$ denote the sequence $a^k, a^{k-1}b, \dots, ab^{k-1}, b^k$, and let $\sigma_k(a, b)$ denote the sum of the integers in $\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)$. Then*

- (a) $g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) = \sigma_{k+1}(a, b) - \sigma_k(a, b) - (a^{k+1} + b^{k+1})$;
- (b) $n(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) = \frac{1}{2}\{\sigma_{k+1}(a, b) - \sigma_k(a, b) - (a^{k+1} + b^{k+1}) + 1\}$.

Proof.

- (a) For $k \geq 1$, by Lemma 1, with $a_1 = a^k$ and $d = b$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) &= bg(a^k, a^{k-1}, a^{k-2}b, \dots, ab^{k-2}, b^{k-1}) + a^k(b - 1) \\ &= bg(a^{k-1}, a^{k-2}b, \dots, ab^{k-2}, b^{k-1}) + a^k(b - 1) \\ &= bg(\mathcal{A}_{k-1}(a, b)) + a^k(b - 1). \end{aligned}$$

If we write $g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) := G_k$, then the sequence $\{G_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ satisfies the first order recurrence

$$G_n = bG_{n-1} + a^n(b - 1), \quad G_1 = g(a, b) = ab - a - b.$$

Dividing both sides of the recurrence by b^n , summing from $n = 2$ to $n = k$ and simplifying, we get

$$\frac{G_k}{b^k} = \frac{G_1}{b} + a^2(b - 1) \frac{b^{k-1} - a^{k-1}}{b^k(b - a)},$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) &= G_k = a^2(b - 1) \frac{b^{k-1} - a^{k-1}}{b - a} + b^{k-1}(ab - a - b) \\ &= \sigma_{k+1}(a, b) - \sigma_k(a, b) - (a^{k+1} + b^{k+1}). \end{aligned}$$

(b) This is similar to part (a). For $k \geq 1$, by Lemma 1, with $a_1 = a^k$ and $d = b$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} n(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) &= bn(a^k, a^{k-1}, a^{k-2}b, \dots, ab^{k-2}, b^{k-1}) + \frac{1}{2}(a^k - 1)(b - 1) \\ &= bn(a^{k-1}, a^{k-2}b, \dots, ab^{k-2}, b^{k-1}) + \frac{1}{2}(a^k - 1)(b - 1) \\ &= bn(\mathcal{A}_{k-1}(a, b)) + \frac{1}{2}(a^k - 1)(b - 1). \end{aligned}$$

If we write $n(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) := N_k$, then the sequence $\{N_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ satisfies the first order recurrence

$$N_n = bN_{n-1} + \frac{1}{2}(a^n - 1)(b - 1), \quad N_1 = n(a, b) = \frac{1}{2}(a - 1)(b - 1).$$

Dividing both sides of the recurrence by b^n , summing from $n = 2$ to $n = k$ and simplifying, we get

$$\frac{N_k}{b^k} = \frac{N_1}{b} + \frac{1}{2}a^2(b - 1)\frac{b^{k-1} - a^{k-1}}{b^k(b - a)} - \frac{1}{2}\frac{b^{k-1} - 1}{b^k},$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} n(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) &= N_k = \frac{1}{2}a^2(b - 1)\frac{b^{k-1} - a^{k-1}}{b - a} - \frac{1}{2}(b^{k-1} - 1) + \frac{1}{2}b^{k-1}(a - 1)(b - 1) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\{1 + g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\{\sigma_{k+1}(a, b) - \sigma_k(a, b) - (a^{k+1} + b^{k+1}) + 1\}. \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

The formulae for both $g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$ and $n(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$ in Theorem 1 display a nice symmetry in the variables a, b . From Theorem 1 we have $n(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) = \frac{1}{2}\{1 + g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))\}$. If m, n are integers with sum $g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$, then it is easy to see that *at most* one of m, n can belong to $\Gamma(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$. On the other hand, if for some such pair m, n , neither belongs to $\Gamma(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$, there would be less than $\frac{1}{2}\{1 + g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))\}$ integers in $\Gamma^c(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$. Thus, for every pair of non-negative integers m, n with sum $g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$, *exactly* one of m, n belong to $\Gamma^c(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$. We use this to derive $n(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$, giving a second proof of the assertion in the second part of Theorem 1.

Theorem 2. *Let a, b, k be positive integers, with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$. Let $\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)$ denote the sequence $a^k, a^{k-1}b, \dots, ab^{k-1}, b^k$, and let $\sigma_k(a, b)$ denote the sum of the integers in $\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)$. If $m + n = g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$, then $m \in \Gamma(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$ if and only if $n \notin \Gamma(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$.*

Proof. Let $m + n = g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$. If $m \in \Gamma(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$, then $n \notin \Gamma(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$, for otherwise $m + n = g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) \in \Gamma(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$, which is impossible.

Conversely, suppose $n \notin \Gamma(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$. If $n < 0$, then $m > g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$ and so $m \in \Gamma(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$. We may therefore assume that $1 \leq n \leq g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$ since both 0 and any integer greater than

$g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$ belong to $\Gamma(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$. Since $n + \lambda b^k \in \Gamma(a^k, a^{k-1}b, \dots, ab^{k-1})$ for all sufficiently large integer λ and $n \notin \Gamma(a^k, a^{k-1}b, \dots, ab^{k-1})$, we may write $n = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} a^{k-i}b^i x_i - b^k x_k$, where $x_i \geq 0$ for $0 \leq i \leq k-1$ and $x_k \geq 1$. If $x_0 > b$ in this representation, by repeatedly using the identity $a^k(x_0 - b) + a^{k-1}b(x_1 + a) = a^k x_0 + a^{k-1}b x_1$ we may assume that $0 \leq x_0 < b$ while maintaining $x_1 \geq 0$. Assuming that x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{j-1} are all non-negative integers less than b for some $j < k$, by repeatedly using the identity $a^{k-j}b^j(x_j - b) + a^{k-j-1}b^{j+1}(x_{j+1} + a) = a^{k-j}b^j x_j + a^{k-j-1}b^{j+1}x_{j+1}$, we may assume that $0 \leq x_j < b$ and still have $x_{j+1} \geq 0$. Thus we may write

$$n = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} a^{k-i}b^i x_i - b^k x_k,$$

with $0 \leq x_i \leq b-1$ for $0 \leq i \leq k-1$, and since $n \notin \Gamma(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$, also $x_k \geq 1$. Writing $g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) = (b-1) \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} a^{k-i}b^i - b^k$, we have

$$m = g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) - n = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} (b-1-x_i)a^{k-i}b^i + (x_k-1)b^k \in \Gamma(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)).$$

This completes the proof. □

Corollary 1. *Let a, b, k be positive integers, with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$. Then*

$$n(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) = \frac{1}{2} \{1 + g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))\}.$$

Proof. Consider pairs $\{m, n\}$ of integers in the interval $[0, g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))]$ with $m + n = g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$. By Theorem 2, exactly one integer from each such pair is in $\Gamma^c(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$. This completes the proof since no integer greater than $g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$ is in $\Gamma^c(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$. □

Remark 1. *Let a, b, k be positive integers, with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$. Then $g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$ is an odd integer.*

The evaluation of g given in Theorem 1 can also be derived by explicitly determining the set \mathcal{S}^* , introduced in [5], since $g(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ is the largest element in $\mathcal{S}^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$. For positive and coprime integers a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k , let $\Gamma(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ denote the non-negative integers in the set $\{a_1 x_1 + a_2 x_2 + \dots + a_k x_k : x_j \geq 0\}$, let m_j denote the least positive integer in $\Gamma(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ that is congruent to $j \pmod{a_1}$ for $1 \leq j \leq a_1 - 1$, and let $\Gamma^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) = \Gamma(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) \setminus \{0\}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) &:= \{n \notin \Gamma(a_1, \dots, a_k) : n + \Gamma^*(a_1, \dots, a_k) \subset \Gamma^*(a_1, \dots, a_k)\} \\ &\subseteq \{m_j - a_1 : 1 \leq j \leq a_1 - 1\}. \end{aligned}$$

Moreover,

$$m_j - a_1 \in \mathcal{S}^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) \iff m_j + m_i > m_{j+i} \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq a_1 - 1. \tag{1}$$

We refer to [5] for more notations and results. With the notations above, we show that $\mathcal{S}^*(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) = \{\sigma_{k+1}(a, b) - \sigma_k(a, b) - (a^{k+1} + b^{k+1})\}$. Since $g(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) \in \mathcal{S}^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$, this further verifies the first result of Theorem 1.

Lemma 2. *Let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k be positive integers with $\gcd(a_2, \dots, a_k) = d$. Define, $a'_j = a_j/d$ for $2 \leq j \leq k$. Let m_j (respectively, m'_j) denote the least positive integer in $\Gamma(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ (resp., in $\Gamma(a_1, a'_2, \dots, a'_k)$) that is congruent to $j \pmod{a_1}$. Then $m_j - a_1 \in \mathcal{S}^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ if and only if $m'_j - a_1 \in \mathcal{S}^*(a_1, a'_2, \dots, a'_k)$ for $1 \leq j \leq a_1 - 1$.*

Proof. Let A denote the sequence a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k and A' the sequence a_1, a'_2, \dots, a'_k . Since each m_j and m'_j must also be representable as a non-negative linear combination of a_2, \dots, a_k and a'_2, \dots, a'_k respectively, it follows that $\{m_j : 1 \leq j \leq a_1 - 1\} = \{dm'_j : 1 \leq j \leq a_1 - 1\}$. Therefore, by (1), $m_j - a_1 \in \mathcal{S}^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ if and only if $m_j + m_i > m_{j+i}$ for $1 \leq i \leq a_1 - 1$ if and only if $m'_j + m'_i > m'_{j+i}$ for $1 \leq i \leq a_1 - 1$ if and only if $m'_j - a_1 \in \mathcal{S}^*(a_1, a'_2, \dots, a'_k)$. This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3. *Let a, b, k be positive integers, with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$. Let $\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)$ denote the sequence $a^k, a^{k-1}b, \dots, ab^{k-1}, b^k$, and let $\sigma_k(a, b)$ denote the sum of the integers in $\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)$. Then $\mathcal{S}^*(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) = \{\sigma_{k+1}(a, b) - \sigma_k(a, b) - (a^{k+1} + b^{k+1})\}$ for $k \geq 1$.*

Proof. We apply Lemma 2 with $A = \mathcal{A}_k(a, b)$ and $a_1 = a^k$. Then $d = b$ and $m_j - a^k \in \mathcal{S}^*(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$ if and only if $\frac{1}{b}m_j - a^k \in \mathcal{S}^*(a^k, a^{k-1}, a^{k-2}b, \dots, ab^{k-2}, b^{k-1}) = \mathcal{S}^*(\mathcal{A}_{k-1}(a, b))$. Therefore, by Theorem 1 in [5], $|\mathcal{S}^*(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))| = |\mathcal{S}^*(\mathcal{A}_1(a, b))| = 1$ for each $k > 1$. Since we have $g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) \in \mathcal{S}^*(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$, there can be no other integer in this set. \square

Corollary 2. *Let a, b, k be positive integers, with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$. Then*

$$g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) = \max \mathcal{S}^*(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) = \sigma_{k+1}(a, b) - \sigma_k(a, b) - (a^{k+1} + b^{k+1}).$$

Remark 2. *The proof of Theorem 3 shows that the sequence of Frobenius numbers $\{g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))\}_{k \geq 1}$ satisfies the recurrence $G_k = bG_{k-1} + a^k(b-1)$ since $g(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b)) = m_j - a^k$ is the only element in $\mathcal{S}^*(\mathcal{A}_k(a, b))$. This result coincides with the result in the first part of Theorem 1.*

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